

ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS THROUGH THE FIELD OF EDUCATION**Sushovan Koner,**

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Abstract:

The most hazardous event of the present century is rapid degradation of environmental quality. The population explosion creates situation like more people needing more food, more energy and more things of daily use, such as housing, clothing and automobiles. Environmental Education not only educates the world population about the natural environment and its problem; but also aims at developing in them the knowledge, attitude and skills necessary to protect the natural balance in environment besides working for its enrichment. Environmental Education is nothing but teaching a man how to interact fully with the surrounding world, so as to improve his inner world. Environmental education enables one to maintain his life. This in turn, helps in the preservation of human race.

Key words: *Environmental Education, School And College Curriculum, Environmental Awareness*

Introduction: The term Awareness is defined as the state or level of consciousness where sense data can be confirmed by an observer. It is conscious of stimulation, arising from within or outside of the person. There is an ever increasing awareness that natural resources, which are mobile, renewable natural resources, exist in limited quantities. Moreover, the available supply can vary considerably during the course of a year, as well from year to year and from region to region

There may not be any confusion that in the current days, the term environmental awareness is one of those terms which driven us to think deeper. It is also an important topic for the global peace and harmony. Water conservation may have different meanings for different people. It may remind us of the possibility of collecting rainwater in small tanks for domestic use, or constructing dams and reservoirs whenever possible to save better water. Water conservation encompasses all this.

Day by day the mankind developing them for a better life and results a bitter one as the environmental imbalance is causing by that. Today for a safe and easy life we are destroying our forthcoming future life. In this context the need of environmental awareness is needed a lot to control this so called development.

One of the best ways to do so is the field of education. The formal education gives us the formal knowledge. The curriculum is centred to make a pupil properly developed. So it is an easy way to awake or aware peoples through this way. Education can develop the pupils through various ways such as-

It can grew up the knowledge of current environmental state

The destructive power of modern lifestyle can be understood

It can focus to the remedies can be taken for environmental balance and so on

So, it is clear that the field of education is one of the strongest way to develop the environmental awareness.

Objectives of the study-

The study is done to come into a conclusion that how much it is important to study environmental studies in different level. The other objectives of the study is as follows-

- To get a clear picture of current environmental awareness among the students
- To get a clear picture about how important is studying environmental studies in the school and college level
- To get a clear idea about how much awareness about environment can be increased through the field of study
- To understand the effectiveness of the current curriculum of environmental study
- Last but not the least to survey what the educational sector thinks about increasing the environmental awareness and its processes.

Methodology-

One set of questionnaire, distributed among the students of four different schools in burdwan (two rural and two urban).The methodology taken for this study is a questionnaire is given to 200 students of class 12. The answer got from them is used as raw material. The answers got from them are the main source of this study. The raw data is examined and the result came after studying the data is this study..

Place of Environmental Study in the field of Education –

Inclusion of Environmental Education at school/college level education has been made compulsory by the Policy maker. As a result of which in West Bengal this subject has been included as a compulsory subject. In school/college curriculum, conservation of water is an important lesson. Theoretical knowledge helps to spread the awareness of conserving natural sources among the students, but the practical application of knowledge is an important factor as well.

Environmental study is studied both as independent subject and in collective form. Environmental study can be referred as multidisciplinary field of study. The environmental aspects of different subjects such as physical sciences, life sciences, geography and its allied subjects and social studies. Environmental aspect means the components directly or indirectly related to the environment and its structure. As example gas and the other chapters which have a close relation with the atmosphere is also a part of environment. It can also said that

we know that the air conditioners components releases the gas CFC and it is very harmful to nature, it is our knowledge from the subject Physical Science. Whereas the immediate and late reaction of this gas towards the Biom can be studied through the life science. And this total study is the component of Environmental study. In this context this is also called as environmental science because of consisting scientific knowledge in this subject.

Place of the subject in the school and college curriculum –

In the school curriculum in west Bengal environmental studies given a good importance since its inclusion in curriculum 2006. In that year it is included in the secondary stage as “PARIBESH PARICHITY” up to class VIII from class VI. In higher secondary it was then included as a compulsory subject.

Current days the school curriculum is revamped and the independent subject Environmental studies are excluded but from Class Vi text books renamed as “ Science and environment”, ‘Geography and environment”, Life Science and environment” etc. up to class Viii. The environmental studies are added with the relevant subjects. This enhances the study of environment by studying simultaneously with the relevant subjects. In the previous curriculum it was a independent subject and it was truly neglected as the marks obtained by the pupils in the subjects doesn’t added to total marks. As well as there is no effect in

calculation of C.G.P.A. In higher secondary level also, the marks obtained is not calculated in the time of admission in higher level or further proceeding. In current curriculum the subject re introduced as a optional elective subject. The major change which can be found that is the ration of Theory and Practical (Previously project work) increased from 70:30 from 40:60. In the previous curriculum it was just only a neglected subject because the practical part consist nothing but only some project work which generally copied to the copy from the book. The syllabus did not force pupils to think constructive.

In the college level it is a compulsory subject consists of 50 marks. The whole examination is written and no scope of practical and project work.

Impact of the subject in environmental awareness –

It is rightly said that education is the manifestation of the perfection already in men. We educate people to utilize the education in their personal life, but some time the bookish knowledge kept in the book and so called educated people is behave like the un educated one. Currently anyone can't deny that after almost 15 years of inclusion of this subject in the curriculum the expected awareness came in the people is very much lower in comparison to the expected value. The awareness came in the people in somewhere from the mass education policy, not by the help of curriculum. It is true that during I deliver this speech or you read the article at about 4 trucks of plastics are thrown to the river Ganges. These are the burning example of the failure of the implication of bookish knowledge to our daily life. But this is also true that in our state after adding this subject to curriculum helped in awareness of environment in a different ways i.e. the mass awareness against pollution. In past few years a lot of planning for plantation are taken and came into effect. A mass steps against deforestation and different issues especially against the use of plastic are seen from the students. This may also the effect of the study of environment studies. The most important drawback of this subject in the field of study is it's "ZERO" effect in the calculation in the result sheet. It is fact that the current situation of Indian education system is its marks centric approach. The students and parents are more conscious about the marks and grades achieved by them or their child than what they actually learn. And this is the main reason that why students get good marks in examination but the implication of those in daily life is nil.

Place of Environmental Study in the field of Education –

Generally we refer the education is the formal education, but there is a large space available outside the formal education. The mass education policy can be taken with the help of Radio and TV. There is a huge prospect on this way as current day people views television almost in every evening. So this can help more. And if we take the formal education, only the bookish knowledge is not enough, but regular group

discussion, seminar, workshop helps a lot to awake awareness in students. The book centric knowledge is mainly kept in books. In the curriculum a lot of scopes available to do field works. The most important part of the awareness is hand to hand works it makes more knowledge to the students. And also the help of NSS & NCC can also be taken

Conclusion –

Thus there is a large scope of increase awareness about environment through the field of education is available. The most important in this field is the change of behaviour. To increase the awareness which is also very important that is the view of teacher and students. It is fact that there is no qualified teacher engaged to teach in school and university level. But M.Sc. in environmental sc. is available in university level. It is fact that today this degree is nothing but a show piece. The teacher of Social Science and Science teaches the subject at school and college level. It is fact that they did not give such importance during teaching which is expected. So at first we need to change our mentality and the rest must be changed automatically. Last but not the least the mass and the parents of the students should also change their mentality and views. And only by increasing awareness we will be able to make a green earth and clean earth.

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